

First principles study on Pd₂ZrGe full heusler alloy using density functional theory

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Abstract:

Electronic structure calculation using density functional theory was carried out for the hypothetical heusler alloy Pd₂ZrGe using PWscf code. The equilibrium lattice parameter was obtained by fitting the energy vs volume data to Murnaghan equation of state. Band structure, density of states and phonon frequencies were calculated for the optimized structure. The structure was optimized using BFGS method for both ionic and volume optimization. Band structure was calculated for both non magnetic and magnetic structure. Pseudopotentials which used for the calculation is GGA type which was generated using Troullier-Martins pseudization method.

References:

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